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THE IMPORTANCE OF KNOWING AND OPERATIONALIZING THE EFFECTIVENESS - EFFICIENCY - LEGALITY IMPERATIVES IN SPORTS MANAGEMENT

Alexandru Virgil VOICU

PhD, University professor, National University of Physical Education and Sports in Bucharest,
Romania

e-mail: alexvirgilweisz@gmail.com
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9857-3592>

Vasiliki Ch. KAPOGIANNI

PhD in Political Science, International & Human Rights Law, Paris II, Panthéon – Assas, Paris, France

e-mail: kapogiannivassiliki@yahoo.fr
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-6512-9054>

Rareș STĂNESCU

PhD, Associate professor, National University of Physical Education and Sports in Bucharest, Romania

e-mail: raresuniv@yahoo.com
<https://orcid.org/0000-0003-4976-0556>

Bogdan-Iosif VOICU

Lawyer, Master's Degree in Law, Master's Degree in the Management of Sports Organizations,
PhD Student in Civil Law at the “Constantin Stere” University in Chisinau, Republic of Moldova

e-mail: alexvirgilweisz@gmail.com
<https://orcid.org/0000-0001-9629-4661>

This paper addresses the importance of legal factors with regards to the best management practice for sports structures/organizations and their activities – seen as an integral part of environmental factors. We emphasize the need to harmonize the national normative framework of sport with the already globalized one that is in continuous dynamics, which reflects the efforts of today's society to have a “Clean Sport” that can only be generated by “Clean Societies”.

These Societies, with respect for human beings and consequently for human rights, are part of the “State of Law” system, an absolute prerequisite for decision-making and legal processes. It would not be possible to build efficiency and effectiveness without respecting the legality – an assertion that also refers to sports management.

Our suggestion and main focus is that the sports manager profession/position, at least in Romania, should be acquired through academic pathways and/or even the qualification provided by a postgraduate degree. Certainly, skills and qualifications are required to gain expertise in Public and Private Law and, of course, in Sports Law.

Consequently, the main idea of this paper is to present the necessity to assimilate the legal culture and recognise the importance of human/athletes' rights in the knowledge of Sports Law experts, as an integral and mandatory part for the training of sports managers.

Keywords: management, sports structures/organizations, sports activities, sports law, State legal system, legal liability, social responsibility, human rights.

IMPORTANȚA CUNOAȘTERII ȘI OPERAȚIONALIZĂRII IMPERATIVELOR EFICACITATE - EFICIENȚĂ - LEGALITATE ÎN MANAGEMENTUL SPORTULUI

Prezentul articol abordează importanța factorilor juridico-legislativi în managementul structurilor/organizațiile sportive și activitățile acestora - văzute ca o parte integrantă a factorilor de mediu. Subliniem necesitatea armonizării cadrului normativ național al sportului cu cel deja globalizat, care se află într-o dinamică continuă, care reflectă eforturile societății actuale de a avea un „Sport curat” care poate fi generat doar de „Societăți curate”.

Aceste societăți, cu respect pentru oameni și pentru drepturile acestora, fac parte din sistemul statelor de drept. Nu este posibil să creăm eficiență și eficacitate în managementul unei organizații fără respectarea legalității - o afirmație care se referă și la managementul sportiv.

Sugestia și obiectivul nostru principal este ca profesia/funția de manager sportiv, cel puțin în România, să fie dobândită în universitățile de profil de știința sportului - la nivel de licență, masterat sau printr-o altă formă de formare postuniversitară. Cu siguranță, competențele profesionale obținute vor viza și cunoștințele de drept public și privat care, la rândul lor, vor putea fi valorizate și în domeniul managementului și dreptului sportului.

În consecință, ideea principală a acestei lucrări este de a prezenta necesitatea asimilării unei solide culturi juridice - parte integrantă și obligatorie a unui curriculum care vizează formarea managerilor sportivi.

Cuvinte-cheie: management, structuri / organizații sportive, activități sportive, drept sportiv, sistem juridic de stat, răspundere juridică, responsabilitate socială, drepturile omului.

L'IMPORTANCE DE CONNAÎTRE ET D'OPÉRATIONNALISER LES IMPÉRATIFS D'EFFICACITÉ - EFFICIENCE - LÉGALITÉ DANS LA GESTION DU SPORT

Cet article traite de l'importance des facteurs juridiques et législatifs dans la gestion des structures/organisations sportives et de leurs activités - considérés comme faisant partie intégrante des facteurs environnementaux. Nous soulignons la nécessité d'harmoniser le cadre normatif national du sport avec celui déjà mondialisé, dans une dynamique continue, qui reflète les efforts de la société actuelle pour avoir un "sport propre" qui ne peut être généré que par des "sociétés propres". Ces sociétés, dans le respect des personnes et de leurs droits, font partie du système des états de droit. Il n'est pas possible de créer de l'efficacité dans la gestion d'une organisation sans respect de la légalité - une déclaration qui fait également référence à la gestion sportive.

Notre principale suggestion et objectif est que la profession / fonction de manager sportif, au moins en Roumanie, soit acquise dans des universités avec un profil sportif - au niveau de licence, de master ou par une autre forme de formation post-universitaire. Certes, les compétences professionnelles acquises cibleront également les connaissances en droit public et privé qui, à leur tour, pourront être valorisées dans le domaine du droit de la gestion et du sport.

En conséquence, l'idée principale de ce travail est de présenter la nécessité d'assimiler une solide culture juridique en tant que partie intégrante et obligatoire d'un programme visant à former des managers sportifs.

Mots-clés: gestion, structures / organisations sportives, activités sportives, droit du sport, responsabilité juridique, responsabilité sociale, droits de l'homme.

ЗНАЧИМОСТЬ ЗНАНИЯ И ПРАКТИЧЕСКОГО ПРИМЕНЕНИЯ ПОНЯТИЙ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ – РЕЗУЛЬТАТИВНОСТИ – ЗАКОННОСТИ В МЕНЕДЖМЕНТЕ СПОРТА

В данной статье рассматривается значимость правовых и законодательных факторов в управлении спортивными структурами / организациями и их деятельностью, которые рассматриваются как неотъемлемая часть факторов окружающей среды. Мы подчеркиваем необходимость гармонизировать национальную нормативно-правовую базу спорта с уже глобализованной, которая находится в непрерывной динамике, что отражает усилия современного общества по созданию «чистого спорта», который может быть создан только «чистыми обществами».

Общества, где с уважением относятся к гражданам и их основным правам, являются частью системы правовых государств. Невозможно добиться эффективности и результативности в управлении организацией без соблюдения законности - утверждение, которое также относится к спортивному менеджменту.

Наша основная цель и задача - получить профессию / должность спортивного менеджера, по крайней мере, в Румынии, в профильных университетах спортивных наук - на уровне бакалавра, магистра или через другую форму постуниверситетского образования. Безусловно, полученные профессиональные компетенции будут также нацелены на знание публичного и частного права, что, в свою очередь, может быть оценено в области менеджмента и спортивного права.

Следовательно, основная идея статьи - представить необходимость усвоения прочной правовой культуры - неотъемлемой и обязательной части учебной программы, направленной на подготовку спортивных менеджеров.

Ключевые слова: менеджмент, спортивные структуры / организации, спортивная деятельность, спортивное право, государственная правовая система, юридическая ответственность, социальная ответственность, права человека.

Introduction

We will try, with the appropriate objectivity required for assessing the role and importance of the legal factor in the management of organizations and physical education and sports activities (according to the provisions of art. 2 of the European Sport Charter), to be ‘marked’ as much as possible by axiological neutralism when referring to behavioral sciences, as is the case in Law, interrelated with management, mainly in the field of economic sciences. Each of us has expressed, in one way or another, the opinion that good management of sports organizations must be subordinated to the imperatives of effectiveness, efficiency and legality.

In order to avoid falling into the trap of ambiguity of the terms used in sport, we decided to operate with the terms, definitions and notions already legalized as a result of developing international normative acts to which many states have adhered.

For instance, we refer to the meaning given to the term ‘sport’, which is actually the domain and the main activity of sports organizations. In the modernity of our society, at European level, the term ‘sport’ is defined, in art. 2, paragraph 1, letter A, of the European Sport Charter, as: “all forms of physical activities which, through organized or unorganized participation, have the purpose of expressing or improving the physical and mental condition, developing social relations or obtaining results in competitions of any level”. The definition was then taken over by the *White Paper on Sport*, which came into effect concomitantly with the birth of the legal force of the Lisbon Treaty, together with the Charter of Fundamental Rights of the European Union.

The sport is assigned a lot of values and functions that are not always consistent with the positive social values and the values of law. When assessing sports behavior or issues related to it, the important principle that “No one is above the law” has not constantly been respected, the sport being often confiscated by illicit interest and pressure groups.

The social dimension of law and sports

Economic sciences (Economics) deal with the study of the production, distribution and consumption of material goods and services; among the issues of interest, we mention: money, banking and financial life, public finances, international eco-

nomy, labor relations, business organization, consumer economy, economy of public facilities, etc.

Economics is a part of social life. But the law has a social dimension. “Why a social dimension?” The law is a complex product of society; its norms intervene in the production process establishing general rules for the repeated daily act of production, distribution and exchange of products and activities. Work requires accepted rigor. Human freedom is only complete insofar as it does not hinder the freedom of others. Human rights cannot be shaped; they can only become realities in an interaction based on the coexistence of freedoms rather than the brutal and damaging assertion of personal rights and interests by others. The superiority of the legal reflection of the necessary correlation between rights and duties, as well as the nobility of the act of justice (as an independent activity in a democratic society), make up the coordinates that decisively mark the social dimension of the law. It is claimed that sport has been commercialized, but also the management of sports organizations and sports activities are subordinated to the law of order.

Sports structures in Romania – the object of sports management

In Romania, art. 2 of the updated Law no. 69 of 2000 states that: para. (3) Physical education and sports include the following activities: physical education, school and university sports, sports for all, performance sports, physical exercises for maintenance, prophylactic or therapeutic purposes; para. (4) The state guarantees the exercise of functions of the public sector and private sector in the fields of physical education and sports, in accordance with the principles of responsible collaboration between all stakeholders; para. (5) The practice of physical education and sports is a right of the person, without any discrimination, guaranteed by the state. The exercise of this right is free and voluntary and is carried out independently or within the association sports structures. (6) The state recognizes and guarantees to the natural and legal person the right to free association for the purpose of establishing sports structures.

The sports structures in Romania are listed in art. 21: a) sports associations; B) sports clubs, including those organized as companies (based on Law no. 31/1990 of companies), educational establishments with a sports program or profile, palaces and clubs for children and students; C) county and Bucharest municipality associations by sports

branch; D) professional leagues; E) national sports federations; F) Automobile Romanian Club, for the activity of sports motoring and karting; G) other national sports organizations. Art. 22 of the Law provides that: (1) sports structures are associations of private law or institutions of public law set up, as the case may be, for the purpose of organizing and administering a sports activity and whose objective is to promote the practice of one or more sports disciplines by their members and the participation in sports activities and competitions. (2) for the purposes and under the conditions established by the law, sports clubs, public legal entities organized under the subordination of central/local public administration bodies or subordinated to public higher education institutions, may operate.

Sports services, efficiency and effectiveness in services and management

Products and services are not produced or consumed alone. Sports services and services, viewed as a commodity, are the main activity of sports organizations, more precisely of public- or private-law sports structures. In this context, the sports company should be regarded as part of the national subsystem of physical education and sports, as part of the whole social system – in the case of Romania. The company or enterprise is not limited only to the economic field, for it has a much larger scope; its object of activity can be from any field, implicitly that of physical education and sports, provided that the economic or social profit is obtained by entrepreneurs.

We will present some considerations regarding the issues of profit and efficiency of physical education and sports structures and activities. The ‘profit’ of sports companies mainly includes the advantage achieved by fulfilling other ‘functional requirements’, other than the commercial ones, that make the subsystem of physical education and sports fulfill other social tasks.

The Romanian society goes to the rule of law and begins to impose its values. Under these conditions, a new societal model is built, namely the liberal compliance model - the law begins to be effective, the simple declaration is exceeded. In the model of liberal compliance, compliance frameworks are determined with ease and there are no interferences in the field of private life - human rights are often invoked, its interest, its obligations and duties less often. The whole private law is based on the idea of interest and especially of

material interest. But should any interest be protected legally? Any interest can give rise to a right? Then in what sense should the idea of interest in legal relationships be taken? The interest cannot be justified in law unless it is in accordance with the conceptions of justice. Only the mere interest - according to the ideal of law - must be consecrated. We believe, we have sufficiently motivated the assertion that the management and the institutions of physical education and sports activities must be subordinated, mainly, to two imperatives: efficiency and effectiveness.

Physical education and sport are a remarkable social activity. The social is based on normative. It is necessary to respect the legal order in the sporting activity. It is important to know the normative framework of these activities - which favor and condition the decision-making process in the physical education and sports system. Thus, if in the management science the content of the legality imperative is not expressly included in the concepts of efficiency and effectiveness, it is our duty to distinguish it as necessary.

The extraordinary development of contemporary sport, over large geographical areas, has led to an increase in the number of participants and the establishment of new sports organizations. The establishment of these new sports organizations has had and has as a consequence the burden of international sports structures. This certainly leads to a lot of questions. One of them would be: what place did international sports structures occupy and can occupy in the legal and economic organization of the world in which they operate? The answer to this question cannot be given only insofar as the institutional identity of these structures relates to the attributes of legitimacy and legality that can generate the efficient and effective management framework. In order for the management of an organization to be considered efficient, it is necessary that the legal factors (of the environment of the sports organization) are not only exploited in the sense of exploiting the opportunities offered by the positive law but also in respect of the state order and the sports order. The sanctions received as a result of the violation of the legal norms, including those pertaining to what we call *Lex Sportiva*, can create great dysfunctions in the management of sports organizations and activities. Therefore, if in the management science the content of the legality imperative is not expressly included in the concepts of efficiency and effectiveness, it is our

duty to distinguish it and propose it as a concept of management science. We consider it necessary to make the following details regarding the terms used in management, namely: efficiency and efficiency. In a recent management dictionary, efficiency means a result or situation characterized by positive outputs of a system, higher than the inputs used. Efficiency reflects performance management at the system level. The achievement of efficiency is a fundamental objective of the management of any organization and their activities. Effectiveness is a feature of a decision, activities, behavior, organizations that designate their ability to ensure the desired effects are achieved, respectively to achieve the proposed objectives, under the preset conditions of time, cost, etc. (Efficiency vs. Effectiveness: Efficiency doing the right things; Effectiveness doing the right things. Peter Drucker in his paper 'About Decision and Efficiency - the Complete Guide to Well-Done Things' stated that 'effectiveness is the knowledge-specific technology of a worker within Organizations. In the case of manual work, we only need efficiency, that is, the ability to do things well, not the ability to do what is good.'")

The legal-legislative factor

At present, we will go through a few examples focusing on the problem of the importance of the legal and legislative factor constituted by the entirety of legal regulations with direct or indirect influence on the physical education and sports organizations and their management - regarded as integrated factors in all the environmental factors comprising: Economic factors, management, technical and technological factors, demographic, socio-cultural and political.

Naturally, the state also plays an important role in the existence and evolution, in terms of social life, of social assistance institutions. Not only that the state regulates by legal norms, the establishment of legal persons with object of physical education and sports activity, their legal capacity, the ways in which they manifest themselves in the dynamics of legal relations, their eventual reorganization and the cessation of their existence as subjects of law, but The state also organizes a complex system of records of their existence. Thus, only for the purposes and under the conditions established by the law, the sports structures can operate legal persons of public law organized under the subordination of the central or local public administration bodies. The possibility of setting up the institutions (struc-

tures) of private law are a consequence of the expression of the right to free association, constitutional law, expressly provided in art. 37 art. Par. (1) of the Constitution of Romania. The constitution of the physical education and sports structures of private law and of law is carried out according to the law - (Ordinance 26/2000 on associations and foundations, Law no. 69/2000 of physical education and sports and its implementing regulation, the New Code Civil law, Law No. 31/1991 on companies and according to the requirements imposed by the specialized public administration).

Increase the professional liability by legalizing it

According to the rule of law no one can be above the law - neither the natural person, nor the legal person and no particular field of activity - in our case we refer to the field of physical education and sport.

It is a recognized fact that the participants in the field of sports activities must also respect: 1. The state order is the one that refers to the administration of the economic means of sports services and benefits, to the issue of employing legal responsibility under its different forms (criminal, contraventional-administrative), civil law, labor law, etc.) thus conferring on the subjects as part of the sports relations established in legal relationships, the guarantee of the protection of the subjective rights through the coercive force of the state. The state order also includes the norms pertaining to the international agreements to which Romania acceded and have the object of sporting activity. Knowledge of the legal system is required for all participants in physical education and sports activities. In physical education and sports activities, values such as life, health, bodily integrity, dignity, justice, equity, freedom, etc. must be protected and promoted. The sanctions received as a result of the violation of the legal norms can create great dysfunctions in the management of the organizations of physical education and sport; The area of the sports field in which the sports regulation (and the game rule) governs; The area of international sports structures, with extension also in the area of national sports structures that elaborate their statutes, regulations, etc. According to the statutes of the international sports federations.

In the traditional doctrine, the Civil Code subjected civil liability, at least technically, to different

regimes, as civil liability is a tort or a contractual liability. Thus, only two forms of liability were inherent in civil law: criminal liability and contractual liability. Today, the New Romanian Civil Code, and the regulations of the EU, regarding the institution of civil legal liability, signal the birth of the third form of civil liability, namely that of professional liability. Thus, we will be in a position to address the issue of civil liability, while at the same time seeing the quality of common law of criminal liability by referring to the new form of civil liability, professional liability.

By identifying the facts of malpractice in the activity of physical education and sport, we will realize not only an image regarding the birth of obligations by creating damages caused to the sportsmen, or third parties, but also by a particularization of the professional liability of those who have the object of sport activity (own Sports and related occupations) including trainers, doctors, physiotherapists, physical education teachers, sports structures, etc. - thus, we will have the support of effective attempts to harmonize the Romanian sports legislation with those of the European and Euro-Atlantic structures in which we have integrated.

The new concept of legal ethics in sports. Professional malpractice

We now refer to the concept of “legal ethics” - a legal order to be imposed on all professionals involved in sports activities. Thus, “the concept of ethics, and even more the legal ethics, is a poly-semantic notion. This situation is favored by the intertwining of morals (ethics), law and professional practices. Studying legal ethics, as part of applied ethics, is an imperative not only for the law of science, but also for moral philosophy. For these reasons, ‘the moral philosophy has been marked, in recent years, by the singular development of its subdomain known as ‘applied ethics’.

The research of the legal ethics as part of the professional ethics is in an incipient phase in Romania. This explains the very low interest, perhaps also for reasons of immorality or amorality of the professionals, the press, and the politicians - to legalize the sports activities. It is true that we are still in the presence of possible interpretations that would not make it possible to hold professionals responsible for the wrongdoing, because it is invoked, in the interest of delaying the employment of the institution of legal responsibility, the

existence of codes of ethics of certain professions.

Under these circumstances, we will be able to “define” (at least theoretically) the legal ethics through the effort of understanding and interpreting the legal norms, followed by their application in absolute good faith.

The ethical-legal principle underlying the employment of civil liability was introduced in the regulations of the Civil Code, in art. 1.349, thus: the breach of the general obligation to respect the legal provisions or the rules established by the custom of the place, if it had as a consequence the attainment of the subjective rights and of the legitimate interests of other persons, obliges the guilty person to complete reparation. In contractual matters, this principle is enshrined in the provisions of art. 1.350 C. Civ. The universalism of this rule makes it applicable in all cases, establishing the legal framework in which the victim can claim and obtain the payment of damages.

This principle has profound moral significance, and it is fair to restore the social balance destroyed by an unlawful act, which ensures the reparation of the damage suffered by the victim, by the one who is guilty of the created situation. This dimension of civil liability results from the fact that, by exercising his freedom, man builds his own personality, but at the same time, he must also take responsibility for his actions. Thus, the man who acts consciously is responsible for his own acts and their consequences, being forced to restore the distorted social balance. True responsibility is always associated with the commutative justice order, which tends to establish a legal reaction meant to remove the consequences of the harmful fact. The relationship between ethics, morals and law thus focuses on the idea of the perpetrator’s guilt. Freedom and responsibility are two complementary and indispensable concepts that characterize human dignity.

Ethical-legal interpretations of civil liability towards professional malpractice

The legal relationship between a professional (sports profession / sports structure) and the beneficiary of the benefit (client, student, performance athlete, spectator, etc.) cannot be completely subordinated to the rules established by a civil contract, on the one hand, but also to those of a liability. Essentially delinquent, on the other hand, which would require a demanding interpretation of the

coordinates of its functionality. This is the reason why the debates on the conditions and the basis of the professional liability tend to detect on its specific elements, of a nature to argue the necessity of harmonizing the legal norm with the realities of the contemporary society, in the face of increasing the danger of prejudice, here referring us to the damages produced in the activity of physical education and sport.

Due to the diversity and complexity of the professional civil liability hypotheses, in the legal plan, it is necessary to establish abstract rules, applicable in all cases of wrongdoing, in order to ensure the more effective protection of the victim, by supporting her in obtaining compensation.

The regulation of the tort and contractual civil liability in the current Civil Code of Romania aims to establish the rules of principle which, in the matter of professional malpractice, are meant to govern the conditions of initiation and success of the action in committing the responsibility, respectively to lead to the restoration of the social balance destroyed by committing a fact that had the consequence of causing harm to another person. In order to ensure full protection of the victim of the crime, it tends to objectify the professional liability of the professional, being engaged in most situations independent of any guilt. Thus, the analysis is transposed into a causal plan, the mere production of the damage triggering the civil liability mechanism. As a special hypothesis of legal liability, civil liability for professional malpractice is that legal report that is born by the violation by certain categories of persons, called generic professionals, of the rules of conduct established by the law or by the professional body to which they belong, causing harm to another person, on whom the obligation to repair it is born.

As can be seen from the definitions set out above, the structure of the legal report of liability for professional malpractice includes the four classic elements of civil liability in general: the injury, the wrongful act of malpractice, the causal link between them and the fault of the responsible person.

Legal harmonization of sports activities via the globalization of sports

The harmonisation of sports activities requires a globalised approach via an international legal framework of acknowledged principles, standards and norms. There are numerous international instruments which reinforce their efforts to stren-

gthen cooperation and present a unified front, striving to eradicate doping, protect clean sport and ensure fundamental rights and human rights are institutionally guaranteed. Sport can be a provider of a role model via values characterising the character and the education of its spirit and with the pillar support of Katowice Declaration, Macolin Convention and other Sports Centers with a focus on clean sport and human rights.

Anti – doping rights act: the Katowice Declaration

A global anti – doping program has recently been set up under the Katowice Declaration, based on the 2021 Code and Standards¹, in order to ensure that fundamental rights within the sports field are clearly set out and are universally applicable. The general concept of “fundamental rights” includes human rights protected on both conventional and constitutional level and EU’s basic freedoms have also been considered. Certainly, the latter, are not human rights technically speaking, however they may play a significant role mainly in doping disputes. According to the WADA code, the fundamental rationale is to preserve what is intrinsically valuable about sport and how we play true and clean. Hence, the Code emphasises on human spirit, body and mind and lists a series of values, namely, “ethics, fair play and honesty; excellence in performance; character and education; fun and joy; teamwork, dedication and commitment but also respect for rules and law².”

Under the auspices of Macolin Convention

Within the spirit of Macolin Convention, focused on the Manipulation of Sports Competitions, a number of concrete priorities were identified and reinforced the phase of the “Macolin Roadmap” which led to its ratification and entered into force the 1st of September 2019³. Enriched by the conclusion of the 3rd International Conference 2018, partners are sharing the challenges and target the threat that sports manipulation poses to sport and society by building trust amongst the actors and implementing strategies of collecting, sharing and processing information. The idea is to create a le-

¹ 2021 Code Review, <https://www.wada-ama.org/en/what-we-do/the-code/2021-code-review>

² *Supra*, 2021 WADA Code Review.

³ Council of Europe, <https://www.coe.int/en/web/sport/about-the-convention-on-the-manipulation-of-sports-competitions>

gal and cultural environment, report suspicious activities via effective mechanisms and focus on prevention by improving education and awareness programs.

Applicability of human rights in sports

As of today, fundamental rights are only applied vertically between the State and the individual which means, the horizontal application between individuals is not embedded within the legal framework. Hence, this classic view of fundamental rights in doping control by sports federations, for instance, would apply to disciplinary proceedings carried out by sports governing bodies that act by virtue of power from the state⁴ which is the case for the French national sports Federations⁵. On the other hand, in most countries, sports federations and their disciplinary bodies are private ones who do not exercise power delegated by the state as it is the case in the UK, US, Germany and Switzerland. Therefore, fundamental rights are inapplicable to doping controls carried out by sports governing bodies which are legally characterized as private entities. The British Government shared the same view when it specified that the Human Rights Act “should have no direct horizontal effect”⁶.

Furthermore, with regards to managing, educating and ensuring equality, diversity and inclusion in sport, we notice that this approach is, so far, mostly limited to the UK, where national sport agencies, equity organizations and sports governing bodies focus on such values and standards. A Sporting Future for All document coming out of the Department for Culture, Media and Sport in 2000, stressed the need to develop policies and strategies to manage and encourage diversity in British Sport, whilst the emergence of a social inclusion discourse was taking place with relation to equality, diversity and sports rights. But talking about the value of diversity is not the same as having diversity because it is in the opposition

⁴ Rudolf Bernhardt, *Fairneff-Garantien in den Europäischen Menschenrechten*, in *Sport, Recht und Ethik* (Stuttgart, 1998), p.54.

⁵ Jean-Christophe Lapouble, *Les droits de l’homme et la lutte contre le dopage: le cas français*, *Petites affiches*, March 5, 1997, pp.12-13.

⁶ Peter Goldsmith, Timothy Dutton, Thomas Keith, Deepak Nambisan, “Human rights and the business lawyer: The impact of the U.K. Human Rights on commerce”, [2001] B.L.I. 55 referring to the ministerial comments made during the passage of the Act through Parliament.

between valuing diversity and being diverse that reproduces itself.

Finally, organisations tend to engage when prompted by legislation and government policy. The equality agenda in sport came from the UK government in the early 1990’s. Important changes were made to equality laws, first by strengthening the Race Relations Act in 2000 and then in planning for a new holistic Equality Act which was enacted in 2010. So, through this Act, many organisations felt that such legislation may be applicable to them and so policy commitments to equality were seen to be one form of proof of meeting statutory legal obligations. In addition, in return for substantial public funding, recipient sport organisations were required to set and meet a range of Key Performance Indicators underpinned by a broader process of modernisation which required sport to professionalise its otherwise voluntary activities. Hence, human rights principles, standards and norms along with equality, diversity and inclusion initiatives become attractive to organisations when they appear to complement wider strategic goals, the so-called business case for equality and prompting a kind of interest convergence with diversity and inclusion policy objectives.

Conclusions

We consider that it is necessary for the legal and legislative factors to be considered of major importance in the management of the institutions that have the object of activity - physical education and sports activities. The training of ‘sports workers’ as well as the management of specialized structures in a developing society, with a development perspective, demands a general culture and modern specialty training - including legal, capable of producing mutations in the way of approach and reception. Which means and should be considered at present the activity of physical education and sport.

Thus, we stress the importance, that the profession/function of sports managers, and in Romania, at least, to be obtained through university, or post-university studies via specialized knowledge of public and private law and, of course, of sports law.

The considerations regarding the stated theme oblige us to support the necessity of assimilating the legal culture and the knowledge of “Sport Law” as an integral and obligatory part in the training of sports managers.

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